

POST-FIRE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES BURNT BY CONE CALORIMETRY AND LARGE-SCALE FIRE TESTING

A.P. Mouritz¹, C.P. Gardiner², Z. Mathys² and C.R. Townsend²

1. *The Sir Lawrence Wackett Centre for Aerospace Design Technology,
Department of Aerospace Engineering, RMIT University,
GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, AUSTRALIA 3001*
2. *Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, DSTO,
GPO Box 4331, Melbourne, AUSTRALIA 3001*

SUMMARY: This paper presents a study assessing the suitability of the cone calorimeter technique for performing low cost, rapid fire tests on fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials to determine their loss in stiffness and strength due to fire. The study involves comparing the thermal environment, ignition mechanisms, fire damage processes, burn-through rates, and post-fire mechanical properties of an FRP composite subjected to an artificial fire inside a cone calorimeter against a large fuel fire. It is found that a higher temperature is required to ignite composites inside a cone calorimeter than in a fuel fire for the same ignition time. The fire damage to the composite caused by cone calorimeter and large fuel fire testing consisted of delamination cracking and char due to combustion of the resin matrix. However, the amount of char and delamination damage was more extensive with the cone calorimeter test for the same ignition time due to the higher temperature required to promote ignition. The mechanical properties of the burnt composites dropped rapidly with increasing exposure times with both fire test methods. The study finds that the cone calorimeter technique can be used to make a preliminary estimation of the reduction to the mechanical properties of composites due to fire, which is a simpler, faster and cheaper technique than the large fuel fire test. Also presented in the paper is an analytical model for predicting the flexural properties of burnt FRP composites.

KEYWORDS: Polymer Matrix Composite, Fire, Cone Calorimetry, Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

A concern with using fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites in aircraft, marine craft, offshore oil drilling platforms, train carriages and bridges is their poor fire resistance and high flammability. Many common types of FRP composites such as carbon/epoxy and glass/polyester laminates ignite and burn when exposed to a hot fire. Large amounts of heat, smoke and fumes are released by composites as they burn, and this aids the spread of the fire and can make it difficult to extinguish the fire. The high flammability of composites has stopped or severely restricted their use in applications where fire is a major risk, such as inside submarines and in many components on offshore drilling platforms. A further concern is that the mechanical properties of composites can be severely degraded by fire, which can cause the distortion and collapse of load-bearing composite structures.

The most reliable methods for determining the effect of fire on the mechanical properties of composite structures is full-scale, quarter scale room, and large panel burn tests. These tests involve exposing large composite structures to a high temperature fire, and then determining the residual mechanical properties of the burnt composite after the fire has been extinguished. These tests can closely replicate the thermal conditions of a fire on an aircraft, ship or drilling platform by having similar flame temperature and flame spread rates. However, these tests are expensive and time-consuming to perform.

Sorathia et al. [1] and Mouritz and Mathys [2-4] have attempted to overcome the need to perform large fire tests by determining the mechanical properties of composites after being burnt using a cone calorimeter. The cone calorimeter is the standard test method for determining many of the fire properties of materials, such as ignition time, mass loss, heat release rate, smoke production, and the chemical composition of fumes [5]. However, cone calorimeters are not designed for the purpose of investigating the reduction to the mechanical properties of composites due to fire. The artificial fire tests performed by Sorathia et al. [1] and Mouritz and Mathys [2-4] involved irradiating small composite coupons with a high heat flux within a cone calorimeter in an attempt to replicate the thermal conditions of a real fire. After the fire tests were complete using a cone calorimeter, the residual mechanical properties of the burnt composite were then measured at room temperature. Benefits of the cone calorimeter technique are that tests can be performed quickly, inexpensively and under well-controlled heating conditions. However, the technique has limitations due to the small sample size that can be tested which may give misleading information on the post-fire mechanical properties of large FRP structures. A further limitation is that a cone calorimeter cannot produce all the conditions of a real fire, such as erratic flaming, fluctuating temperature and flash-over. Therefore, uncertainty remains about the capability of the cone calorimeter to degrade the mechanical properties of composite materials in the same way as large fires. If the cone calorimeter technique is reliable, however, it can be used for inexpensive and rapid assessments of the reduction to the mechanical properties of composites due to fire.

The aim of this paper is to assess the usefulness of the cone calorimeter technique in the determination of the post-fire mechanical properties of FRP composites. This is achieved by comparing the temperature, fire damage, burn through rates, and post-fire flexural properties of a FRP composite that has been burnt using a cone calorimeter against the same material burnt in a large-scale fire test. The composite is a glass-reinforced polyester (GRP) laminate that is used in boats, ships and offshore structures. A further aim of the paper is to determine whether a model proposed by Mouritz and Mathys [3-4] for predicting the post-fire flexural modulus and strength of composites burnt in a cone calorimeter can also be used to determine the post-fire flexural properties of composites burnt in a real fire.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Composite Material

Fire tests were performed on a GRP composite made with E-glass woven fabric and polyester resin. The glass was a plain woven fabric with an areal weight of 1.35 kg/m² supplied by Colan Industries. The resin was an isophthalic polyester supplied by Dulux Australia. The composite was fabricated into flat rectangular panels using the wet hand lay-up process and then cured at room temperature for several weeks. The composite had a fibre volume content of about 34% and void content of 2-4%. Small composite panels measuring 240 mm long, 150 mm wide and about 12.0 mm thick were made for testing in a cone calorimeter. Large panels measuring 1350 mm long, 550 mm wide and 13.5 mm thick were made for large-scale fire testing. The large panels were slightly thicker than the small panels because of the difficulty in accurately controlling panel thickness using the wet lay-up process. The large panels for fuel fire testing has a fibre volume content of about 30% and a void content of 2-4%.

Fire Test Techniques

Artificial fire tests were performed on the small composite panels using a Stanton Redcroft cone calorimeter. Figure 1 shows a general view of the cone calorimeter and a close-up view of a burning panel. The artificial fire tests were performed by the rapid heating to one surface of the panels using a high-energy heating coil. It is possible to produce heat fluxes between 10 and 120 kW/m² using standard cone calorimeters, which heats the panel surface from

about 300 to 900°C with increasing heat flux. However, for this study the heat flux of 50 kW/m² was chosen because it caused the GRP panel to ignite after heating for 30 seconds. Greene suggests that the heat flux of 50 kW/m² is about the heat energy radiated by a medium intensity room fire [6]. The panels were exposed to the heat flux for different times up to 10 minutes. A thermocouple was placed at the heat-exposed surface of the panel to measure the temperature reached by the composite inside the cone calorimeter. A second thermocouple was used to measure the air temperature close to the heating coil. At the end of the fire tests, the burning composite panels were removed from the cone calorimeter, extinguished and then cooled to room temperature.

Figure 1. (a) The cone calorimeter and (b) a burning panel inside the calorimeter.

Large-scale fire tests were performed by burning large composite panels in a kerosene fuel fire. Kerosene was used as the fuel instead of lube oil or petroleum because it produces less smoke when it burns. Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram and photograph of the large fire test. In the tests, the panels were suspended 280 mm above a large tray containing burning kerosene. This distance was chosen because the flame at this height caused the composite panel to ignite after 30 seconds, which is the same ignition time as for the small panel tested in the cone calorimeter at the heat flux of 50 kW/m². Only the underside of the large panels that faced the fire were burnt because the topside surface was protected from the flame with a thermal insulation blanket. The large panels were exposed to the fuel fire for various times up to 10 minutes, and then the burning composites were extinguished and cooled to room temperature. Thermocouples were placed between the fuel tray and panel to measure the flame temperature and were also placed on the panel surface to monitor the temperature of the composite.

Assessment of Fire Damage & Post-Fire Flexural Properties

Fire damage to the small and large composite panels was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and ultrasonics. Specimens were taken from the burnt panels for SEM examination to identify the types and distribution of fire damage caused by the cone calorimeter and fuel fire tests. The SEM was performed using a Cambridge Stereoscan Mk2 S250 Instrument microscope operated at a voltage of 20 kV in the back-scattered imaging mode. The depth and distribution of fire-induced cracks in the panels was measured using pulse-echo ultrasonics. The ultrasonics was performed at a frequency of 0.5 MHz using a Krautkramer-Branson flaw detector (Model USD-15).

The post-fire flexural properties of the burnt composites were determined at room temperature in quarter-point bending according to ASTM D790 (Method 2) specifications [7]. After testing in the cone calorimeter, the small panels were sliced into coupons measuring 240 mm long, 25 mm wide and 12.0 thick. Similarly, after the fuel fire tests, coupons were cut from the large panels to a size of 240 mm long, 25 mm wide and 13.5 thick. The burnt surface of the coupons was placed against the two load points of the quarter-point load fixture so it experienced bending-induced compression under the applied load. The coupons were loaded to failure at a cross-head speed of 4.3 mm/min.

The apparent post-fire flexural modulus of the burnt composite was determined by:

$$E = 1.7 \frac{L^3 m}{bd^3} \quad (1)$$

where m is the gradient of the linear portion of the load-displacement curve, L is the support span, and b and d are the width and thickness of the coupon. The apparent flexural strength was calculated using:

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{4bd^2} \quad (2)$$

where P is the maximum applied load.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. (a) Schematic diagram and (b) photograph of the large-scale fire test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The temperature conditions for the cone calorimeter and large fire tests are compared in Figure 3. The results show that the surface temperature of the small composite panel inside the cone calorimeter increases rapidly with time to approximately 800°C. However the air temperature, when no specimen is present, is only about 465°C. There is a substantial difference in temperature between the composite surface and air temperature inside the cone calorimeter. This is mainly due to the fact that in the cone calorimeter a high proportion of heat is absorbed by the composite because the heat is from a radiative source. In comparison, the flame temperature of the kerosene fire was similar to the surface temperature of the panel, approximately 300°C. This occurrence is most likely due to the lower radiation emitted and the higher heat losses due to convection from a fire compared to the cone calorimeter. The temperatures were also significantly lower for the kerosene fuel fire because it was not possible to generate higher flame temperatures, which is determined by the heat energy released by combustion of the kerosene fuel. It is possible, however, to generate a higher flame temperature by using fuel with a higher heat release energy.

Despite these differences in temperature, both the small panel tested in the cone calorimeter and the large panel exposed to the fuel fire ignited and began burning after only 30 seconds. Figure 3 shows that at 30 seconds the panel tested in the cone calorimeter reached 350°C, which is about the auto-ignition temperature of polyester resin [8]. Ignition of the composite in the cone calorimeter occurs by combustion of volatile gases released from the polyester resin as it is thermally degraded at elevated temperature. In comparison, the large panel in the fuel fire test reached only 170°C when it ignited at 30 seconds, and this lower ignition temperature is probably due to the naked flame (which is not present in the cone calorimeter test) igniting the polyester resin. Therefore, the mechanism by which composite materials ignite when exposed to an artificial fire in a cone calorimeter or a fuel fire is different.

Figure 3. Comparison of temperatures generated in the cone calorimeter and fuel fire tests.

The fire damage to the composite panels caused by the cone calorimeter and fuel fire was examined after the fire tests. It was found that after the composite surface ignited, the panels tested in the cone calorimeter or fuel fire began to char due to combustion of the polyester resin matrix. In both fire tests, the char formed as a well-defined layer that could be clearly distinguished from the unburnt portion of the panel, as shown in Figure 4. Shown in figure 4b

is a scanning electron micrograph of the microstructure of the charred composite, and it is seen to consist only of glass fibres because the polyester resin has been burnt away by the fire. In the unburnt portion of the composite the polyester matrix was not severely degraded, however long delamination cracks developed in the panels, and these formed by thermal strains generated by the cone calorimeter and fuel fire tests. In summary, the heat damage caused in the artificial fire test using the cone calorimeter and the large fire test was identical, and consisted principally of charring and delamination cracking.

Figure 4. Fire damage to the composite caused by cone calorimeter and fuel fire testing.

(a) Schematic showing distribution of fire damage through-the-thickness of the composite panel, with the lines showing the location of delamination cracks. (b) Microstructure of the char layer. (c) Delamination cracks in the unburnt portion of the composite panel.

The amount of charring and delamination cracking to the composite panels increased with heating time for both the cone calorimeter and fuel fire tests. Figure 5 compares the thickness of the char layer (d_c) and maximum depth of delamination cracks (d_d) below the burnt surface for the two test methods. It is seen that the amount of charring and cracking is higher with the cone calorimeter technique. The higher burn-through rate is because the cone calorimeter technique generated higher temperatures than the fuel fire test.

The residual flexural modulus and strength of the composite after being burnt in the cone calorimeter or fuel fire are compared in Figure 6. The original flexural properties of the GRP composite in the large panel are slightly lower because of the higher thickness compared with the small GRP panel. With the composite tested by the cone calorimeter or fuel fire test the flexural properties drop rapidly with increasing heating time, and for times longer than ~400 seconds the composite has little residual stiffness and strength. The reduction is due to the increased amount of charring to the composite with longer heating times. It is seen that the flexural properties are slightly higher when the composite was burnt in the fuel fire, and this

is because the amount of fire damage consisting of char and delamination cracking caused by this test was less than that caused by the cone calorimeter. The amount of damage caused by the cone calorimeter method was greater because of the higher surface temperature required to promote ignition. Despite the small difference in measured values, the results in figure 6 indicate that the cone calorimeter technique can be used to make an inexpensive and rapid assessment of the likely reduction to the flexural properties of FRP composite materials burnt in a large fuel fire.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Effect of increasing heating time on the (a) char layer thickness and (b) depth of delamination cracking.

Mouritz and Mathys [3,4] have shown that the flexural properties of burnt FRP materials can be determined using a model based on rule-of-mixtures where the flexural properties of the

char and unburnt portions of the composite are combined. Using this approach, the flexural modulus of a burnt FRP composite beam when loaded in quarter-point bending can be determined by [3,4]:

$$E = \left\{ \frac{4(d - d_n)^3 + 4(d_n - d_c)^3}{d^3} + 4 \cdot \frac{E_c}{E_o} \cdot \frac{[d_n^3 - (d_n - d_c)^3]}{d^3} \right\} \cdot E_o \quad (3)$$

where E_c and E_o are the flexural modulus of the char and unburnt composite, and for the GRP panels E_c equals 0 GPa. d and d_c are the thickness of the composite and char layer, respectively, while d_n is the distance from the charred surface to the neutral bending axis of the composite, which is calculated using:

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Effect of heating time on the post-fire flexural (a) modulus and (b) strength. The curves show the theoretical reductions to the flexural properties.

$$d_n = \frac{E_o d^2 - d_c^2 (E_o - E_c)}{2E_o d + 2E_c d_c - 2E_o d_c} \quad (4)$$

The curves in figure 6a shows the theoretical reduction to the flexural modulus of the composite with increasing heating time calculated using equation 3. There is excellent agreement between the calculated and measured flexural modulus when the composite was burnt in the cone calorimeter or fuel fire.

The flexural strength of a burnt composite beam when loaded in quarter-point bending can be calculated using equation 1, where the failure load, P , is determined using [3,4]:

$$P = \frac{8\sigma_o b}{3L} \left\{ \frac{(d - d_n)^3 + (d_n - d_c)^3}{(d - d_n)} + \frac{E_c}{E_o} \cdot \frac{[d_n^3 - (d_n - d_c)^3]}{(d - d_n)} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where σ_o is the flexural strength is the unburnt composite. The curves in figure 6b show the calculated reduction to the flexural strength, and there is some agreement with the measured strength values for both the cone calorimeter and fuel fire tests. This shows that the residual flexural properties of FRP composites burnt in a fire can be predicted with good accuracy using the model.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has compared the fire damage created from a small artificial fire using a cone calorimeter and a large fire produced with burning fuel. In the cone calorimeter, ignition will occur only when the concentration of volatile gases released from a thermally decomposing composite reaches a sufficiently high concentration to ignite when exposed to a small spark. In a fuel fire, on the other hand, ignition of a composite occurs more easily because of the large flame. Hence, for the same ignition time, higher temperatures are required to ignite a composite inside a cone calorimeter that therefore increases the rate of burn-through for the cone calorimetry specimens in comparison to the fuel fire specimens. Despite these differences, the fire damage to composites caused by a cone calorimeter and fuel fire are the same, and consist principally of charring and delamination cracking. The reductions to the flexural modulus and strength of a composite with increasing heating time are similar after fire testing inside a cone calorimeter and large fuel fire. Based on these findings, it is proposed that the cone calorimeter technique can be used to make a preliminary estimation of the reduction to the mechanical properties of composites due to fire, which is a simpler, faster and a cheaper technique than large fuel fire tests. The study also finds that the reduction to the flexural properties of FRP composites burnt inside a cone calorimeter or large fuel fire can be predicted using an analytical model proposed by Mouritz and Mathys [3,4].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Country Fire Authority, Victoria, for the use of their facility to perform to large fuel fire tests.

REFERENCES

1. Sorathia, U., Lyon, R., Gann, R. and Gritz, L., "Materials and fire threat", *SAMPE J.* May/June 1996, Vol. 32, pp. 8-15.
2. Mouritz, A.P. and Mathys, Z., "Mechanical properties of fire-damaged glass-reinforced phenolic composites", *Fire & Mats.*, 2000, Vol. 34, pp. 67-75.
3. Mouritz, A.P. and Mathys, Z., "Post-fire mechanical properties of marine polymer composites", *Comp. Struct.*, 1999, Vol. 47, pp. 643-653.

4. Mouritz, A.P. and Mathys, Z., "Post-fire mechanical properties of glass-reinforced polyester composites", *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, (in press).
5. Greene, E., "Fire performance of composite materials for naval applications", *Proc. Marine Comp. Symp.*, 8-10 Nov 1993, pp. G11-1 to G11-31.
6. "Method of test for heat and smoke release rates for materials and products using an oxygen consumption calorimeter", Australian/New Zealand Standard AS/NZS 3837:1998.
7. "Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials", ASTM D790-95a, 1995.
8. Bansal, R.J., Mittal, J. and Singh, P., "Thermal stability and degradation studies of polyester resins", *J. App. Poly. Sci.*, 1989, Vol. 37, pp. 1901-1908.